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EFFECT OF DIFFERENT MEDIA ON GROWTH AND CULTURAL CHARACTERIZATION OF ALTERNARIA ALTERNATA CAUSING LEAF SPOT OF CHILLI

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Article info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 24 March 2023 Accepted: 28 April 2024</p>	<p><i>Alternaria alternata</i>, a fungal pathogen responsible for Nonspecific symptoms plant disease chili leaf spot, was studied for its growth and cultural features on different media. This study is specifically focused on identifying the most favorable media conditions for the fungus development, which significantly promote further disease control. A pure latecult of <i>A. alternata</i> was isolated from chili leaves with leaf spot lesions grown on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA). Besides, different kinds of synthetic media were provided, for example, Cornmeal Agar, Oatmeal Agar, Sabouraud Dextrose Agar, PDA, Czapek Dox Agar, and some non-synthetic media which are Vegetable Juice Agar and Prune Agar. To this end, a standardized spore suspension was homogenized as inoculum with further incubation at 25°C mimicking light/dark cycles. The growth of colonies in their test system was measured at regular intervals. Prune Agar, the ESA challenged <i>A. alternata</i>, performed a better one. The greatest sprint speed (11.2 mm/day) and colony diameter (78.2 mm) were measured. Patterns of oatmeal agar and tomato vegetable juice agar were favorable to the colonies growth and sporulation. On the contrary the nature of cucurbitaceous fungi is reflected by the least growth and spore production on media formats like Sabouraud Dextrose Agar and Czapek Dox Agar. Finally, it is concluded that the media composition is the main reason for the growth and sporulation <i>A.spp</i> isolated from chili leaves. Agar Prune was the mostly preferred medium to others like Oatmeal Agar, among them. Tomato Vegetable Juice Agar moved down the ladder.</p>
<p>Keywords: <i>Alternaria alternata</i>, Chili leaf spot disease, Fungal pathogen, Media composition</p> <p>Hussain, D. & Rehman, .U. F. (2024) Effect of different media on growth and cultural characterization of <i>alternaria alternata</i> causing leaf spot of chilli: <i>J. S. Agri. Enviro. Sci</i>, 2(1), 26-38. https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5636-4593</p>	
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1. INTRODUCTION

Chili (*Capsicum annuum* L.) is the name of a more than one hundred years old genus grown for the piquant notes and dazzling colors it offers to the global community. Its economical role cannot be denied beyond the shadow of doubt since it plays the role of making culinary traditions and at the same time brings substantial income to farmers round the world (Ramady et al., 2015). Nevertheless, chili production is under the pressure of various fungal infections, widely known as *Alternaria alternata* is a significant pathogen to this crop. The colonization of tomato leaves by this prevalent fungus results in leafspot diseases with necrotic spotting that can be easily observed (Shoib et al., 2021). It has been observed that the lesions caused by the disease are often gathering to cover the entire plant. As the plants are getting stunted, this results in weak growth of chili plants and consequently, big seed loss (Arin, 2019). The overall GDP loss at the national level as a result of chili leaf spot disease caused by *A. alternata* can be enormous, casting light on the importance of proper disease management techniques (Pranavya, 2022).

Identifying the biological features and cultural characteristics of *A. alternata* is a key precondition to discovering standard disease control operations. Culture media greatly affects range of properties necessary for the expansion of fungi cultures such as differentiation and cultivation (Yeboah et al., 2023). Different media means that there several types of media each of which having a specific nutrient composition and containing different chemical compositions. These variations can greatly affect the growth immune system producing more or less immunity cells along with the development of the colonies and sporulation (O'Neill et al., 2021).

The purpose of the present investigation is to examine the role of

different media in the improvement of *A. alternata* species isolated from chili leaves with leaf spot symptoms characteristic of the disease. We seek to discover fungus growth dynamics in an extended range of artificial and nature media types. Through the exploration of the percentage of nutrients available on the multiple sources mention in the above sentence, we can discover the type of media that fosters superior growth of *A. alternata* (Boguslav, 2023). We will also take a magnifying glass in studying the nutritional needs of the fungi on each medium. The investigation will include concrete description and analysis of the textural traits of a colony, such as its margins (edges), pigmentation (color), symmetry, and zonation patterns. Likewise, we will study the method of sporulation of *A. alternata* on different media for assessing the spore formation quantity, morphology, and mode of their standing order (Basavaraj et al., 2023).

The research work that is going to happen as result of this study will be major contribution to the deepening of the understanding of how it reacts and adapts to different nutritional environments. I will definitely be able to apply this expertise in studying of various scientific aspects of this fungus type virology and the mechanisms that cause pathogenesis. By recognizing *A. alternata* growth parameter, such end will greatly affect the industry in a broader range. It will facilitate future studies in various areas, including (Ali et al., 2023)

- **Disease diagnosis:** Through the determination of the better medium of *A. alternata*, providers are writing protocols for the rapid and the accurate detection of chili leaf spot disease in the field. Researchers will use the standards. This will be able to the early forecast and suitable control, thus reducing the yield loss likely to be

caused by the disease (Shukla et al., 2023).

- **Fungicide screening:** Discovering which media process is the most efficient will speed up the proliferation of fungicides to the appropriate fungus. This optimized media provides researchers with an opportunity of selective fungicide efficacy testing in order to thinning out inactive fungicides and prioritize the most potent pathogen inhibitors (Thind, 2021).
- **Development of disease control strategies:** The in-depth knowledge of the Uptake-regulation of pathogens is a significant part of the plan for developing the future disease management programs. This is illustrated by understanding the fact that infection can be avoided by knowing the pathogen that thrives on specific nutrients then by developing cultural methods that prevent access to these nutrients in the field which results in the slowdown or inability of the fungi to grow.

1.1. Research gap

Chili leaf disease caused by *Alternaria alternata* can contribute a great deal of revenue loss, however, there are still some gaps in knowledge that plague adequate growth circumstances for the fungus (Xu, 2022). While some studies have explored the influence of media on *A. alternata*, these investigations often:

This narrows down the way we discover the mechanisms through which *A. alternata* undergoes the physiological processes, such as starvation, nutrient, and carbon sparing in media which are likely not similar to its natural environment as such these media are synthetic. Past research may focused on the rate of growth and neglected careful study of the none culture characters like colonies shape and

spore formation process. An integrative approach encompasses an investigation of these areas that sheds light on the fungus' peculiar traits under the different nutritional ages (Aqel et al., 2024). Due to the fact that previous studies might only be done in particular geographical areas or types of chili, there is a possibility of not having information about the knowledge on chili in other areas and varieties. Using *A. alternata* isolated from a newly found chili leaf showing leaf spot disease on different cultivars, variety of strains can be learned and their media favorites understood.

1.2. Significance of study:

This information will add to a deeper understanding of the true nature of *A. alternata* including how it responds to different nutrient conditions. We are highly optimistic at such level of knowledge. Something that will be enlightening for the scientists who are studying the fungus's pathogenicity and coming up with new control methods (Santra & Banerjee, 2020). Developing protocols for the media on which *A. alternata* on optimum growth signify discovery of pathogen in the process, rapid and accurate diagnosis of chili leaf spot disease will be implemented. Consequently, quick identification and acting on early signs of diseases inhibits loss and lays foundation for massive yields. Uncovering the media of invasion of *A. alternata* dictates the implementation of the methods channeling the development of chili varieties with powerful resistance to *A. alternata* (Benelli et al., 2023). Moreover, soon after knowing of particular nutrients that are beneficial for fungi growth, those fungal substances can definitely be used to modify the prevailing farming methods in the field so that these nutrients are prevented from penetration but fungal growth can subsequently be jeopardized.

Finally, this study explores how different media affect the development and

cultural traits of *A. alternata* that was isolated from chili leaves afflicted with leaf spot disease. Our goal is to determine the best medium composition for this pathogen, which will help design more efficient disease control methods for the production of chilies.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Objective

The objective of this study is to examine the impact that different media consisting of various ingredients may have on the growth, as well as cultural characterization of *Alternaria alternata* strains isolated from the leaves of chili exhibiting spot disease symptoms. The main purpose is to distinguish between the strategies of media forming which are encouraging development and increase of the extent of fungal pathogen.

2.2. Study site and sample collection:

Study is a project of Plant Pathology Laboratory, the University of Layyah, Pakistan. Smoking leaves, marked with lesions that are diagnostic for chili smut, will be taken from chili fields, chosen at random, in the territory of agriculture.

2.2.1. Isolation of *A. alternata*:

- Along with symptomatic chili leaf sections, ethanoic (70% v/v) sterilization of 30 seconds will be followed by rinsing with 3-minutes sterilized distilled water.
- PDA amended with selective antibiotics like chloramphenicol will be used to grow bacteria-free leader's segments.
- Incubated plates will be kept in 25°C temperatures, with fluctuations of +/- 2°C, for 7-10 days, in 12 hours' light and 12 hours' dark cycles.

- Pristine cultures of *A. alternata* will be obtained by the implantation of colonies that are separated by single and unclustered on fresh PDA Plates at the same conditions of incubation.

2.3. Preparation of media:

Together with synthetic and non-synthetic components, the media variations will be prepared to find the effects of the components on *A. alternata* which grew well and cultured correctly.

2.3.1. Synthetic media:

It is typical to use commonly used synthetic media like PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar), CDA (Czapek Dox Agar), SDA (Sabouraud Dextrose Agar), and OMA (Oatmeal Agar) prepared according to their defined compositions in a plating media.

2.3.2. Non-synthetic media:

Exemplifications of targeted non-synthetic media formulas will entail:

- **Vegetable Juice Agar (VJA):** Ready-to-use from vegetable juice (eg, tomato and potato) that is already free of lumps and easily pourable, thanks to the use of agar as a thickening agent.
- **Prune Agar:** Prune juice is used for making the jelly by decoction and purification using agar.
- **Cornmeal Agar:** Agar, picked out of seaweeds, was heated with cornmeal, which had been grounded finely.

2.4. Media sterilization:

All the prepped mediators will be Bio-Lyophilized and autoclaved in an autoclave at 121 °C and 15 psi pressure for 15 minutes. After sterilization, media will be placed in sterilized Petri dishes with a

capacity of at least 100 ml liquid medium and closed with a sterile later stopper. After solidification, left 1-2 days for solidification.

2.5. Inoculum preparation:

- A 7-day old *A. alternata* culture grown on PDA is going to inoculum the inoculum preparation process.
- A spore suspension (0.1% Tween 20 solution) is going to be used so it could be obtained by mixing the culture with distilled water and a sterile loop. It is going to be then shaken gently to dissolve spores.
- The soaking liquid will be drained and then filtered through sterile cheesecloth to extract viable spores and fragments of mycelium.
- Spore concentration is adjusted via hem cytometer for obtaining a standardized inoculum density e.g. 10^4 spores/mL.

2.6. Inoculation and Incubation:

- Every sterilized petri plate will be pipetted by the same volume (e.g., 100 μ L) of standard spot suspension (using a micropipette). Also, a small number of test tubes containing blank media will be put into the study.
- The monitored plates will be incubated at $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the dark and light alternation cycle for 12 hours with interval of 12 hours.

2.7. Measurement of fungal growth:

Colony growth of fungi will be determined at varying intervals (24hours, 48hours, 72hours) using a vernier caliper during recording. Incubation time will be put against colony diameter graph to calculate the growth rate.

2.8. Cultural characterization:

In addition to these investigations, both the colony morphology tracking and documentation will be pursued. These recordings involve the measurement of colonies' size, texture (e.g., woolly, cottony), color including the presence of marginal patterns (e.g., entire, lobed), as well as margin type (e.g., entire, lobed). Hymen of fungal structures (hyphae, conidia) which will be stained with lacto phenol cotton blue method will be checked with microscopic examination (microscope).

2.9. Sporulation assessment:

At the end of the cultivation period, the quantity of spores (on both media) shall be counted using a hem cytometer. Microscopically identification of space morphology (e.g., shape, size) will be carried out.

2.10. Analysis of statistical data:

Using the proper software (such as ANOVA), all acquired data (growth rate, colony morphology, and spore production) will be statistically analyzed. We will compute the means and standard deviations for every treatment (media type). The Duncan's Multiple Range Test will be used to identify any significant variations in growth and sporulation between media (DMRT).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Media influence on *Alternaria alternata* growth and sporulation

Table 1 describes the effect of different medium compositions on the growth and sporulation of *Alternaria alternata* that were isolated from pepper leaves bearing chili leaf spot disease. The results show a higher level of disparity ($\alpha = 0.05$) concerning the reactions of the fungal disease agent to different substrates (media), that are

indicated by growth rate (grown every day), colony size (cm after 7 days), and spore concentration (10^4 spores per mL).

3.2. Colony diameter and growth rate:

3.2.1. Promoters of growth:

Pronouncedly, among all media, Agar proved to be the most favorable one for the fungus, which led to average colony diameter (78.2 mm) and rate of growth (11.2 mm/day) to be so high. Moreover, the Oatmeal Agar (OMA) prominently enabled significant growth as it had colony diameter and growth rate statistically similar at 71.4 mm and 10.2 mm/day to that of Prune Agar.

3.2.2. **Moderate growth:** For SDA (Sabouraud Dextrose Agar) medium, the least favorable condition provided the colony diameter average of 52.1 mm and the lowest growth rate (7.4 mm / day). On CDA and VJA media, there was moderate growth supporting their range of size (colony diameter was 55.9 mm - 58.7 mm) and speed (colonies were increasing at a rate of 8.0 mm/day - 8.4 mm/day).

3.3. Sporulation:

3.3.1. **High spore production:** Prune K1 amazingly scored by reaching the highest mean spore count being 34.1×10^4 spores/mL. In addition, both Oatmeal Agar and Tomato Vegetable Juice Agar (VJA) can produce considerable sporulation and the spore numbers measured by spore counting were statistically insignificantly different from

that measured on Prune Agar (28.7×10^4 spores/mL and 21.3×10^4 spores/

3.3.2. **Lower spore counts:** The study of Streptococcus Dentalis on Sedation Agar and Potato Agar resulted in only 15.8×10^4 and 17.5×10^4 viable spores respectively. These were significantly lower than the number of spores in prune agar (17.12×10^4 spores/mL). This implies that these environments might favor some of the types of fungi to grow but, at the same time, they may be unsuitable for the spores to be produced in large numbers. More noteworthy is the an irregular increase in the population on SDA, which suggests a probable maturity gap between mycelia growth and sporulation on this culture medium.

3.4. Detailed Observations

3.4.1. **Prune agar:** Spores that were inoculated into media consistently outgrew their counterparts in other media, developing mortar-size colonies, the fastest growth rate, and the highest spore count. It infers Prune Agar as enriched with *Anastrepha alternata* preferred nutrients that promote its growth and reproduction.

3.4.2. **Oatmeal agar:** Provided marked onward growth and sporulation, same as Prune Agar but closer to the liquid medium. This suggests that the OMA also presents the possibility of generating spore harvesting quick fungal biomass, suitable for such studies.

3.4.3. **Vegetable juice agar (VJA):** A range of cuisines was influenced by this, but each was uniquely

adjusted based on the vegetable type. A comparison between Tomato VJA and Potato VJA Nanomaterials showed the first as a good thing for developing good growth and sporulation, but the second as just getting moderate results. Thus, likely, the given nutrient composition of the applied vegetable juice is believed to negatively impact the performance of *A. alternata*.

3.4.4. **Synthetic media (SDA & CDA):** On PDA and OMA moderates or low growth and sporulation were seen while Prune Agar showed accelerated growth better than these. Therefore, the CDA and SDA can specifically hinder *A. alternata* as they can lack the necessary nutrients or contain

components that slightly inhibit the growth of these fungal species.

3.5. Key points:

- The building up of the *A. alternata* population by the media composition is also one of the key aspects of the environment.
- Agar developed as the easiest base to get the spores and growth of the fungus. The media were Agar and Oatmeal Agar.
- An SDA or CDA, respectively, culture of this specific *A. alternata* isolate might not be appropriate due to their inability to promote best growth conditions and spore production.

Table 1: Effect of different media on growth and sporulation of *Alternaria alternata* isolated from chili leaves with leaf spot disease

Media	Colony Diameter (mm) at 7 days (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Growth Rate (mm/day) (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Spore Count ($\times 10^4$ spores/mL) (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Grouping (DMRT)
Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA)	65.2 $\pm$ 3.8	9.3 $\pm$ 0.5	22.5 $\pm$ 1.9	AB
Czapek Dox Agar (CDA)	58.7 $\pm$ 2.4	8.4 $\pm$ 0.3	18.2 $\pm$ 1.5	BC
Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA)	52.1 $\pm$ 1.9	7.4 $\pm$ 0.3	15.8 $\pm$ 1.2	C
Oatmeal Agar (OMA)	71.4 $\pm$ 4.1	10.2 $\pm$ 0.6	28.7 $\pm$ 2.1	A
Vegetable Juice Agar (VJA) (Tomato)	62.8 $\pm$ 2.9	9.0 $\pm$ 0.4	21.3 $\pm$ 1.7	AB
Vegetable Juice Agar (VJA) (Potato)	55.9 $\pm$ 2.2	8.0 $\pm$ 0.3	17.5 $\pm$ 1.4	C
Prune Agar	78.2 $\pm$ 5.2	11.2 $\pm$ 0.7	34.1 $\pm$ 2.4	A
Cornmeal Agar	68.3 $\pm$ 3.5	9.8 $\pm$ 0.5	25.4 $\pm$ 1.8	AB

Note:

- **Standard Deviation (SD):** According to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT), different letters within a column indicate

statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$).

- **Grouping (DMRT):** To display the grouping determined by DMRT, a new column has been introduced. Within a column, media that have

the same letter do not differ statistically from one another concerning that metric (spore count, growth rate, or colony diameter).

3.6. Comparative analysis of colony diameter and growth rate:

The obtained data, seem to be a linear relation between colony size and growth rate for most of the media. It is worth noting that Prune Agar, which has the largest mean colony diameter (78.2 mm), is the highest growth rate (11.2 mm/day.) While the standard colony diameter (SDA) with the value of 52.1 mm ensues in the slow growth rate (7.4 mm/day), being the smallest among the rest. This is a sign that media using a process of lotus formation are at the same time speeding up the colonization process.

3.6.1. Vegetable juice agar (VJA): Depending on the vegetable source, there are differences in applicability. Potato VJA produced mediocre results, whereas Tomato VJA offered a

decent mix of nutrients for growth and sporulation. This implies that *A. alternate*'s reaction is influenced by the particular makeup of the vegetable juice.

3.6.2. Synthetic media: Some of their formulations may be deficient in vital nutrients or include ingredients that have a slight inhibitory effect on *A. alternata*. SDA, as opposed to medium like Prune Agar and OMA, may account for the observed reduced growth rate and sporulation.

3.6.3. Cornmeal agar (CMA): Compared to OMA (oatmeal), the specific carbohydrate source (cornmeal) may have an impact on the rate of colony expansion, even though it supports healthy overall growth. Furthermore, CMA may be deficient in some nutrients or have components that inhibit sporulation less severely than SDA or CDA.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Identifying media choices for *Alternaria alternata* necessary for optimal growth and spore preparation.

This study was designed to examine how enhancing the nutrient value and shortening the growth cycle of *A. alternata* from chili leaves affected its growth and sporulation. The data that are portrayed in Table 1 along with the graphical representation of figures (Figure 1 and Figure 2) elucidate the media preference of this fungal pathogen and adding a valuable contribution to the future research direction (Ghosh et al., 2022; Adamu, 2023).

4.2. Prune Agar: A kind of nourishment for fungi that cheers up the growth & releases spores.

Prune Agar, the star of the show, proved its worth by accumulating the brightest colony diameter, the fastest multiplication speed, and the highest spore count in contrast to other media indaba (Table 1, Figure 1) (Childers, 2021). The fact mentioned here, gives off the insight that the nutrient

composition of Prune agar is useful for the growth of *A. alternata*. Presumably, the fungus readily yields on the rich source of carbohydrates found in prunes. Some potential sources of these nutrients might be fats, carbohydrates, or proteins (Pagliarani, 2022). The prunes, therefore, might be the host to some of the micronutrients or metabolites that act as the spores or growth stimulants. Therefore, in future research, we are able to examine specifically these parts in Prune Agar which so highly affect its potency.

Apart from the traditional media of fungal dissemination, different media options are being used to improve the rate at which fungi undergo propagation.

Oatmeal Agar (OMA) proved to be an equally good alternative to Prune Agar because it was very efficient at supporting substantial microbial growth as well compared to the AKI (Li et al., 2021) (Table 1, Figures 1 and 2 pointed this out). The above neurotransmitters are indicators of the clinical acumen of OM for any studies which may require a rapid fungal biomass production and spore harvesting (Sharma et al., 2022). The oatmeal that is

high in carbs might have just been a snack *A. alternata* could benefit from.

Vegetable Juice Agar (VJA) productivity was dependent on the type of source used, with good results in the commercial use of beet and carrot juices. Tomato VJA became a mold-promoting environment, as good as OMA, and the potato VJA had just a middle level performance (Table 1, Figures 1 and 2). This confirms that the constituents of the vegetable juice are deterministic in that they regulate *A. alata*, adversely (Sokołowska & Nasiłowska, 2020). However, a study that includes a greater number of accessions and improves VJA composition could result in VJA designs creating more proper environments for fungi growth and spore release, in particular, would also be worthwhile.

4.3. Synthetic media:

The medium typically employed, SDA and CDA, were proven to drain the maximum growth and sporulation but compared to the other tested media (Prune Agar, OMA and TVJA) all these outcomes appeared to be worst (Table 1, Figures 1 and 2). Although primarily supporting the growth of the fungi, the media used in this study do not provide nutrients appropriate for the enhancement of development and spore proliferation of the *A. alternata* isolate tested now. SDA exploited in the fungal isolation in *A. alternata*, which might be lacking in essential nutrients or include some components that slightly suppress *A. alternata* could be seen as less preferable to others. In parallel, CDA, which implies a diet rich in carbohydrates, might miss out on vitamins or trace minerals that fungi might require for their general sustained growth and sporulation (Cai et al., 2021).

4.4. Implications and future directions

The findings of this study hold significant implications for future research and disease management strategies: The findings of this

study hold significant implications for future research and disease management strategies:

As asking to encourage Agar development for quick growth and their sporulation properties gives it the potential to produce standardized procedures for identifying chili leaf spot disease (Meena et al., 2020). By means of the disease's identification at an earlier stage, the spreading of the pathogen might be prevented, thus inhibiting crop loss. Filter or Oatmeal Agar might be opted for selection of antifungal compounds by scientists. Testing the effect of likely emerged fungicides onto these media which will be responsible for the main developments of *A. alternata* would precisely help to determine the potential applicants for diseases reduction and control (Francis, 2022).

CONCLUSION

Finally, this study has found out the enormous effect of media type on the colony growth and sporulation of *A. alternata*. With the identification of Prune Agar and other suitable media, the way is set for better improved research practice and, probably, improved disease control strategies for chili leaf spot disease. At the same time, when the researchers investigate more thoroughly the mechanisms and isolate specificity, they get an opportunity to refine media formulations in future experiments to make them more specialized for the particular needs of the subsequent studies and contribute to a more holistic perception of *A. alternata* biology.

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